

A Study on Effectiveness of Google Pay Application among Students

Ameena Febin T

MCom

DOI-

Abstract

Digital payment system is gaining popularity due to the 'Digital India' campaign introduced by the government of India. Through this article it aims to provide a simple evaluation of effectiveness of Google Pay application in the students. This article has relevance as it is concerned about awareness level among students, security issues while using digital payment applications, satisfaction level and popularity enjoyed by them and security concerns they have while using Google Pay. The government is taking initiatives to move the country towards a cashless 1 economy and increase the use of digital transactions. The main motto of the Indian government is to make the Indian economy 'Cashless, Faceless, Paperless 2'. The spread of digital payment usage varies unevenly between countries partly due to difference in factors such as quality of regularity framework and readiness of telecommunication infrastructure, marketing capabilities, trust, ease of use etc.

Keynotes: Digital payment, Google pays, cashless economy, Digital

Rationale of the study

The study on effectiveness of Google Pay application helps to identify the attitude towards Google Pay as a digital payment system. It shows the awareness level of students towards the digital payment applications in general. The study helps to identify the problems and security issues faced while using Google Pay application. Altogether it shows the level of effectiveness of Google Pay application among students.

Objective of the study

1. To know the familiarity of digital payment applications among students.
2. To understand the satisfaction level about the usage of Google Pay Application.
3. To know about the attitude towards the security issues while using Google Pay application.
4. To identify the preference of Google Pay application among other Digital payment Applications.

Hypothesis

Wide acceptability of Google pay from digital payment system.

Satisfactory level of students by using Google pay.

Security issues faced by students while using Google pay.

Research Methodology

The area of the study has been confined to only students. The methodology used in the study

Tools For Data Collection

The present study was conducted in college and the primary data were collected by distributing questionnaire among students to evaluate the effectiveness of Google Pay application.

Tools For Dataanalysis

The tools used for data analysis are:

involves collection of data through primary and secondary sources.

Research Design

The present study is descriptive in nature. The major use of descriptive research is explanation of state of affairs, as it exists at present.

Population

The population of the present study includes the students.

SAMPLING AREA

The data for the study collected from students in college.

Sampling Unit

The students from college are the sampling unit for the study.

Sample Size

In this study, 60 numbers of students were selected as sample out of the total population.

SAMPLING DESIGN

The sample of respondents for the study was selected by using convenient sampling technique.

Sources Of Data

Primary Data

The primary data for the study were collected from various categories of 60 sample respondents by distributing questionnaire.

Secondary Data

The secondary data for the study were collected from various printed publications and from the online media.

Comparative Analysis¹

Percentage Analysis²

¹ Comparing items to one another and distinguishing their similarities and differences

² Dividing the value by the total value and then multiplying the result by 100

In this study tables, charts and diagrams are also constructed and presented for interpreting the results of the study.

Suggestions

There are still few respondents who prefer traditional mode of banking³. So proper awareness about online banking should be provided.

As the future of payments depend upon digital payment systems, the familiarity of digital payment systems needed to be improved among the younger generations like students.

Google Pay application still lacks some features. So, it should be broadened enough to use all features conveniently.

There is a tight competition among the digital payment applications. Therefore, Google should advance the functioning of Google Pay application which will help to increase the satisfaction of users. Proper awareness about Google Pay security issues should be given to people who lack awareness.

Banks should provide support to Google Pay users when any kind of fraudulent activities⁴ happened to its users.

The security of Google Pay further needs to be improved to protect its users from security threats.

Conclusions

This study shows that Google Pay application has a wide acceptability among the students and most of them prefer Google Pay application than other digital payment applications like Paytm, PhonePe etc. The students who use Google Pay are satisfied with the application and its services and they have a better knowledge in security threat mitigation. But the lack of awareness in Google Pay security issues caused the students to experience such issues like cashback / refund fraud, phishing, etc. Hence the study stresses on that they should be vigilant while using Google Pay as well as performing online transactions. According to the findings of the current study, Google Pay is a widely used digital payment application among students and it helps them to make payments easily. Therefore, the study can be concluded that Google Pay application is very effective among students.

References

Journals

1. Dr. S.Poongodi, Dr. P.Jayanthi, Ms. R.Ramya (2021), Users Perception towards Google Pay – Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology 18(1). ISSN 1567-214.
2. Dr. C. Mallesha and Priyanka Godugu (2021), Trends in Digital Payments system in
3. India-A Study on Google Pay, PhonePe and Paytm, International Journal of Scientific

Development and Research (IJSDR), Volume: 6, Issue: 2.

4. Dr. G. Pasupathi, G. Reka (2019), "A Study on Customers' Perception towards Mobile Wallet with Special Reference to Google Pay", A journal of composition theory.
5. Tanzila Ayaz Sayed et.al (2018), "A Study on Customer Satisfaction Level and Customer Perception of E-Payment App Services with Special Reference to Pune City", International Journal of Management, Technology and Engineering, Vol. No.8 (12), Pp.4442-4453.
7. Shivanji Jaiswal & Pankaj Joge (2018), "A Study on Consumer Acceptance of Mobile Wallet with Special reference to Durg/Bhilai", International Journal of Advanced in Management, Technology & Engineering Science, ISSN No.: 2249-7455, Vol 8, Issue III, March 2018.
10. K.Sumavally, Dr. K.Hema Divya (2018), "A study on Digital payments in India with Perspective of consumers adoption", International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, ISSN: 1314-3395, Volume 118 No. 24, May 2018.
12. Ahuja A, and Joshi R. (2018), "Customer Perception towards Mobile Wallet", IJRDO-Journal of Business Management, Vol.4 (1), January, pp.52-60.
13. Abhijit and Harmeet (2017), "Gpay usage by smartphone users and also Attempts to analyse the varied obstacles faced by the Gpay users", EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR) – Volume: 7, Issue: 8.
14. Manikandan, S., and J. Mary Jayakodi. (2017) "An empirical study on consumer Adoption of mobile wallet with special reference to Chennai city." International Journal Of Research – Granthalaya 5.5 (2017): 107-115.
15. Roopali Batra, Neha Kalra (2016), "Are Digital Wallets The New Currency? Apeejay Journal of Management and Technology, Vol 11, No 1, January 2016 Books
16. Kothari C R, (2020), Research Methodology: Methods and Technique, New age Publishers, New Delhi.
17. Jaspal Singh, (2019), Digital Payments in India: Background, Trends and Opportunities, New century publications.
18. Indian Institute of Banking and Finance, (2019), Digital Banking, Taxmann Publications.

Websites

1. <https://www.researchgate.net>
2. <https://pay.google.com>
3. <http://www.jctjournal.com>
4. <https://archives.palarch.nl>

³ Banks with physical presence

⁴ Phishing,spoofing etc